

METHODS FOR ORGANIZING DATA EXCHANGE IN A DISTRIBUTED MEDICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (MIS)

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Introduction. *In the modern world of information technology, distributed medical information systems (MIS) play a key role in the healthcare sector. They ensure effective management of medical data, quality control of services provided and improved communication between doctors, medical staff and patients.*

This article discusses various methods for organizing data exchange within distributed MIS. The authors analyze the advantages and disadvantages of each of them, and also discuss prospects for development and optimization to improve the quality of medical services provided.

We have already noted that healthcare informatization is closely related to the aggregation of data in external storages and the exchange of data between relevant information sources, therefore data warehouses must ensure work in distributed information sources. The results of studies of multiplicative structures for the MIS of medical organizations representing a complex internal organization are presented in a number of publications [1–3].

We noted above that in medical information information, the key object of information presentation is the document, and all other materials are an appendix to derivative documents. It should also be noted that we have well recommended an approach to document-oriented data replication, where the replicated object is a document that encapsulates everything necessary to understand the content of the document within its structure. This approach greatly simplifies the problem of data exchange, because First of all, reduce the range of replication types. This basically leads to a number of accounts related to document-oriented data storage:

- determination of globally unique identifiers of data objects;
- reduction of some keys (foreign keys) to a minimum;
- implementation of the concept of versioning, commercial at the document level, as a whole object, and not at some level of its individual parts.

Thus, semi-structured and unstructured documents are replicated automatically by majority majority of opinions:

- ·modification of an amended entry is resolved by accepting two versions in their chronological order;
- ·deleting a modified entry determines the acceptance of the version and its subsequent deletion;
- ·deletion of a deleted entry is resolved by deletion.

Changing a deleted entry is done either manually or by setting a policy: deleting or saving such an entry.

For structured data objects containing foreign keys, there is no reliable MasterMaster replication method that allows data to change on any of the communicating nodes (servers). To solve this problem, data clustering by nodes is used: each cluster of additional keys by data keys can be changed strictly on one master node. For example, in the simplest case, the system can be configured so that the reference data allows editing exclusively on the main node. In more complex

cases, fragments can be separated from the reference data and edited on local nodes. This data organization allows the use of standard methods of replication of permission resources, established for the Master-Slave configuration (“master-slave”).

An additional complication of replication is the replication of wired ledgers. In transactions, unlike master data and semi-structured documents, there is a need to execute business rules after receiving data: the node that receives the package of documents and the structure of operations with them must create rules (for example, acceptable threshold elements for accounts) as a result of the replication session will not be violated. Solution methods. Options of this type can be selected:

- ·receive data incrementally, observing the chronology of operations;
- ·a single master node is offered that has the right to conduct group operations;
- ·the terms of the conclusion and return the refusal of acceptance to the sending node to explicitly resolve the conflict;
- ·automation of permitting decisions.

Below we will consider the listed methods in more detail.

The incremental method (where the action “accept” or “reject” gives the result for each operation separately, not for the management pack) and maintaining chronology solves two problems. Firstly, observing the natural chronology of operations in normal situations, ensuring that all business rules are followed, because Situations where the invoice is generated earlier than the crediting are excluded are excluded. It should be noted here that the chronology of operations does not necessarily coincide with the chronology of document entry. The goal of a business-correct accounting ledger is to ensure the integrity of items at any given time precisely in the chronology of transactions. Secondly, in the event of a conflict, operations on the same account with different nodes, at least, operations preceding the conflict situation will be carried out.

In addition, incrementality involves skipping only operations and changes to accounts, which results in a conflict.

In other words, only those operations (together with their source documents) that provide the chain of motion for the conflicting remainder are rejected from the replication package. However, it should be noted that skipping only the conflict operation, and not the entire chain, can lead to induced conflicts that aggravate the situation.

The complexity of this method lies in the fact that sometimes accounts are required that aggregate operations performed at different nodes, but using different analytics. For example, a budgeting system in a distributed architecture assumes a general plan of budget accounts, as well as a procedure for organizing operations based on account data, indicating the identifier of your organization as an analytical slice.

Ensuring that there is no conflict here is possible through consistent configuration available for running operational analytics across each node and business rules. When agreeing in this case, it is assumed that the prohibiting business rules are constructed in such a way that, in each specific application case, they are calculated based on a data set generated strictly on one node.

Obviously, the methods described above to prevent insufficient factors - there is always the possibility of misconfiguration or induced results arising from factors accumulated and not yet resolved in previous replication sessions. In this case, replication of accounting registers other than the standard ones can cause a typical type of conflict: violation of the business rules of the accounting register.

The recipient node that detects an operation that results in the impossibility of executing a business rule rejects the entire chain of operations for the movement of the conflicting remainder from the replication package and sends a message to the administrator.

The system administrator analyzes the cause of the conflict, exploits it, and conducts out-of-band session replication, delivering only data from the resolved conflict.

Some types of issues that are not related to configuration errors may be resolved automatically. For example, when accounting for accounts used to account for financial and material assets between organizations, a typical situation is when the receiving organization replicates receipt transactions to the main node for which the main node does not yet have transaction costs from the sending organization. In this case, it is important to reconcile some business rules in the usual calculation, with an allowance for the time gap. We will call such business rules “weak”.

The replication mechanism uses operations that violate weak business rules, but after the replication cycle has completed, when the recipient node has an up-to-date set of operations with all nodes, the execution of weak business rules is rechecked and, if necessary, the administrator is notified.

Conclusion

Currently, work continues in [2] to study the problems of data presentation in a medical information system. Currently, MIS must be adapted to changing conditions and interaction in complex information systems, which increases the requirements for technologies for presenting, storing and transmitting data. The implementation of the proposed approaches should improve the consumer qualities of the developed information systems, expand their capabilities and reduce the costs of developing and supporting application solutions.

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